

What Financial Incentives Currently Exist For Sustainable Waste Management, And How Effective Are They?

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Abstract

This report is a review of the currently existing financial incentives that support sustainable waste management, with a focus on India and some comparative global examples. Strategies and incentives such as tax rebates, subsidies, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), Pay-As-You-Throw (PAYT) schemes, blended finance, and green bonds are identified as key drivers of recycling, waste reduction, and inclusion of informal workers. There is evidence that shows these incentives can improve collection efficiency, enhance financial sustainability, and create social benefits, but their effectiveness is limited by weak enforcement, infrastructure gaps, and uneven implementation. Overall, financial incentives are powerful tools for circular waste management, but they must be integrated into broader institutional and policy frameworks to achieve resilient and inclusive urban sustainability.

Keywords:

Financial Incentives, Effective waste management, Solid Waste Management, policies for sustainable waste management, Deposit Refund Schemes (DRS), Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), Pay-As-You-Throw (PAYT) schemes, Blended finance, Green bonds

Introduction

Effective waste management is directly linked to reducing urban pollution, mitigating health hazards, and improving the quality of life in urban centers. A vast body of research reports that financial incentives encourage communities to adopt clean practices and contribute to a healthy urban environment, which is vital for combating climate change. Understanding what kind of incentives exist for sustainable waste management is vital to improving what works to promote sustainable development as a whole, especially in areas where waste management systems vary across regions and are largely informal.

This research aims to assess:

1. What financial incentives currently exist to promote sustainable textile waste management?
2. How effective have these incentives been in practice?

By focusing on this local case, the study addresses both the community needs of waste workers and micro-manufacturers and the policy gaps that hinder financial participation in circular practices. This report aims to contribute to research in SAGE's consortium of Clean Healthy Cities by conducting a review of recent policies and existing financial incentives to promote well-being, improved health outcomes, and environmental sustainability in urban areas (*Thakker & Sun, 2023*).

Marappanapalya Ward (erstwhile Ward 44, N.B. ward numbers and boundaries are subject to change) in northwest Bengaluru houses a high concentration of textile manufacturing and garment units, many of which operate in the informal sector or as micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs). However, these industries have limited access to formal recycling channels or financial incentives for sustainable waste practices (*Enviu, 2025*).

The need for financial and policy-based incentives to support sustainable waste management, like in Ward 44, is underscored by three key issues:

1. A lack of formal recycling infrastructure.
2. Limited awareness and enforcement of sustainability practices.
3. Poor market linkages and inadequate financial support for waste segregation and reuse.

There is a growing momentum to address these gaps. Initiatives such as Hasiru Dala's Hasiru Batte program and the Textile Recovery Facility (TRF) in Bengaluru have shown that inclusive, circular models can integrate waste pickers, reduce landfill dependency, and create economic value from textile waste (*Hasiru Dala, 2024*).

Background and Purpose of Financial Incentives

With annual municipal waste generation projected to rise from 2.0 billion tonnes in 2020 to 3.88 billion tonnes by 2050, the global waste crisis is escalating, and this necessitates robust financial mechanisms (*World Bank Group, 2025; Zhang et al., 2025; World Bank Group, 2022*).

Developing countries and their urban centers are disproportionately affected. Usually, over 90% of waste disposed of is in unregulated dumps or openly burned, leading to severe health, safety, and environmental consequences, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and plastic pollution. Effective waste management is also financially demanding as it consumes around 20-50% of municipal budgets (*World Bank Group, 2022*).

Financial incentives, especially market-based mechanisms, are vital for aligning economic interests with ecological responsibility. They aim to bridge funding gaps, incentivize recycling, and hold producers accountable. The World Bank Group is a major financier of solid waste management, having provided approximately US\$5.13 billion in official development financing from 2003 to 2021, and accounting for 35% of the global total. Their approach combines infrastructure financing with policy reform loans, results-based payments, critical knowledge, and capacity-building, all tailored to local contexts (*World Bank Group, 2025*). This support aims to enhance local health, economic growth, and resilience while simultaneously cutting GHG emissions and plastic pollution.

There are multiple incentives, which range from corporate social responsibilities and government schemes like subsidies to payments for segregated waste, that have been implemented worldwide for waste management with varying degrees of success. The Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) approach holds manufacturers accountable for the entire lifecycle of their products, especially for take-back, recycling, and final disposal (*OECD 14*). By internalizing waste management costs, EPR motivates producers to design eco-friendly products and reduce waste. EPR has seen varying degrees of success in managing electronic waste (*Compagnoni, 2022*).

Under Pay-As-You-Throw (PAYT) schemes, households are charged based on the amount of waste they discard, creating a direct economic incentive to minimize waste and increase recycling. This model has been effective in various regions, leading to significant reductions in waste generation. *Valente (2022)* suggests that lower waste prices work well as people throw away much less unsorted waste, recycle more, and overall generate less trash. At high PAYT prices, people don't necessarily produce less total waste; they just recycle more. Lower-income areas are more sensitive to waste pricing, meaning they change their waste habits more when prices go up. The success of these models often depends on the level of community awareness, the availability of infrastructure, and the effectiveness of enforcement mechanisms. For instance, a deposit refund scheme may be highly effective in a region with well-established recycling infrastructure, but less so in a region where such infrastructure is lacking. The success of these programs also depends on how well they are communicated and understood by the public (*Sustainability Directory, 2025*).

Recycling Rewards and Buy-Back Schemes: Some programs offer financial rewards or credits to individuals who recycle specific materials. For instance, startups like Trashie provide consumers with credits redeemable at partner retailers in exchange for recycling textiles, thereby encouraging recycling and reducing landfill waste. Multiple companies have started focusing their efforts on recyclability, especially in the clothing industry, to tackle the problems of fast fashion. These companies provide credit and discounts to their customers for bringing in clothes to be recycled. They also focus their efforts on using sustainable materials for their clothes, and big chain stores, like Primark, have focused their efforts on selling apparel made of recycled material at discounts and competitive prices. In India, many waste management companies have now focused their efforts on collaborating with organizations to make waste disposal easier (*Trade India; "Top 10 Waste Management"*). Furthermore,

recycling companies are leading the charge against climate change by focusing on developing new ways to manage garbage and turn it into usable resources.

National Action Plan for Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) Management (2015) in India – An Action plan proposed by the government to reduce solid waste in India has provided guidelines for the states to reduce MSW. It also encourages financial incentives to reduce waste and focuses on waste segregation at the intra-city level. India's Green Credit Programme incentivizes voluntary environmental actions by providing credits for activities such as afforestation, water conservation, sustainable agriculture, and waste management. These credits can be monetized or used to offset environmental obligations, promoting proactive participation in sustainability efforts. The long-term effects of this program have yet to be realized.

Tax breaks and subsidies can make investments in waste reduction technologies and infrastructure more economically attractive for businesses, promoting innovation and the adoption of cleaner production methods (*Sustainability Directory 2025*). India offers lower GST rates for waste management services, such as waste collection, treatment, and disposal, as compared to standard GST rates. This reduced rate aims to make waste management services more cost-effective and encourage their adoption (*FirstGreen Consulting (2023) "Waste Management in India"*). *Pacheo (2012)* reports that the lack of fiscal subsidies was one of the key reasons for poor recycling in Rio, and predicts that employing subsidies would encourage people to recycle their waste and increase overall recycling capacity.

Methods

This literature review on financial incentives and their effectiveness in sustainable waste management systems was conducted following the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework. This will be followed by the selection and exclusion of literature, ensuring scientific rigor, reproducibility, and transparency.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for screening papers/articles:

Included: Qualitative data from government sources, reports, and articles published post-2020

Excluded: Reports, articles, and news that do not feature financial incentives for waste management practices and their effectiveness or results after policy implementation. Qualitative data and information published prior to 2020.

Data source and screening:

- A thorough literature review is being conducted using digital research repositories such as Research Rabbit, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, PubMed, and Google Search as the primary search engine.
- This search is focused on key words like: “financial incentives”, "sustainable waste management," "key waste management practices," "incentivising waste management," "waste management incentives in india", "India’s incentives for waste management", “financing waste management”, “extended producer responsibility (EPR)”, “corporate social responsibility (CSR)”, “financing EPR”, “financing CSR”, “government benefits for waste management”, “waste management policies”, “waste management strategies for MSMEs”.
- Additionally, the relevant research articles and reports mentioned in the references were also analyzed.

Data collection and selection process, and data items:

- Here, data refers to qualitative data, which is reported alongside policy results and implementation.
- All reports used for the study were first skimmed over to check for the requisite information, and then, using “Ctrl+F” or “Cmd+F” key, information was examined in detail by the independent investigator and analysed for usage.
- Studies that didn’t report financial incentives (verbatim) but focused on them in other forms, such as funding opportunities, taxes, subsidies, or areas for exploring R&D, were picked up and used to improve and support the primary research question.

Results

Study Selection:

- After running a Google Search for official documentation about incentives for waste management and related policies, several pages of results were found, but had to be carefully filtered.

- Certain reports focused on recommendations, but these were found to have: (i) no basis, or (ii) were pre-2020, or (iii) opinion pieces. Only factual information from government sources and news articles has been chosen and analysed for this study.

Results of the study:

Description of the Key Financial Incentives for Sustainable Waste Management, several of which are existing and are recommended to promote sustainable waste management practices within the circular economy framework by *the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (MoHUA, 2021)* in India:

- **Tax Rebates and GST Reductions:** MoHUA reports that policy & regulatory gaps, such as a lack of incentives to encourage recycled products and complex EPR frameworks, amongst others, have inhibited the potential of dry waste in the circular economy.
 - They propose a rebate in tax/GST on recycled products to increase their competitiveness against virgin materials. Specifically, a reduction of GST to 5% for recycled products.
 - Particularly in the Construction and Demolition (C&D) sector, several policies were proposed regarding this. GST for C&D waste products was reduced from 18% to 5%.
 - The green tax for the transportation of C&D waste products was waived.
 - Electricity load in C&D waste plants charged at the industrial rate was reduced, and a single window environmental clearance was suggested for the setting up of a C&D waste processing plant (*MoHUA, 2021*).
- **Extended Producer Responsibility:** This would make producers financially responsible for end-of-life treatment, often via compliance fees, take-back obligations, or eco-modulated fees. India has been focusing on EPR to reduce dry waste generation. For instance, the Wash the Dabba initiative in Bangalore can be incentivized in a similar way to scale it to other cities (i.e., the take-out containers can be returned to the producers for some benefits) (*I, 2024*).
- **Direct Financial Assistance and Subsidies:** The Ministry of Chemicals & Fertilizers provides Market Development Assistance (MDA) of ₹1,500 per ton on city compost

to scale up production and consumption. It is recommended to extend this MDA to compost produced from biomethanation and sludge (*MoHUA, 2021*).

Current Policies in India as per MoHUA (2021)

- Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) is providing financial assistance for the setting up of Waste to Energy Plants as follows:
 - Biogas projects receive a capital subsidy of ₹1 crore for every 12,000 m³ of biogas generated per day, with a ceiling of ₹10 crore per project.
 - Power projects are eligible for a subsidy of ₹3 crore per MW, also capped at ₹10 crore per project. Existing biogas plants that convert to power generation can avail a subsidy of ₹2 crore per MW.
 - For bio-CNG/enriched biogas (CBG), a subsidy of ₹4 crore for 4800kgs/day of CBG generated per day [up to ₹10 crore/project]. For existing biogas units switching to CBG, the subsidy is only ₹3 crore.

Recommendations and Action Plans for Wet Waste Circularity (*MoHUA, 2021*)

National level:

- The Ministry of Finance (MoF) will waive customs duties on imports related to biomethanation plants and extend GST concessions.
- The Ministry of Chemicals and Fertilizers (MoCF) will extend the MDA scheme for city compost to include compost produced from biomethanation and will tag the sale of this compost with chemical fertilizers.

State level:

- States will provide incentives to private developers to encourage investment in the biogas economy.
- States will develop district-level Waste Processing Parks under the authority of the District Collector to help local bodies meet statutory requirements.
- States and Urban Local Bodies (ULBs) will strengthen waste segregation at the collection level by empowering safai karamcharis to levy fines or penalties on unsegregated waste and to refuse collection in such cases.
- The State Urban Development Department (SUDD) and State Pollution Control Boards (SPCBs) will impose heavy fines or taxes on the indiscriminate dumping of wet waste in landfills or open land.

Recommendations and Action Plans for Dry Waste Circularity (*MoHUA, 2021*)

National level:

Policy interventions:

- Waste management is now treated as a priority sector for lending and environmental permits.
- GST was lowered to 5% for alternative and recycled goods.
- Expanded Extended Producer Responsibility to include paper, textiles, rubber, metals, and glass.
- Allocated funding for R&D of product redesign, remanufacturing, and alternate materials based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and MFA.

Infrastructure interventions:

- Introduced innovative financing mechanisms for recycling infrastructure, including a Credit Guarantee Fund. This serves as a financial backstop to banks and lending institutions to provide credit for waste management and recycling projects.
- Funded waste management-related start-ups.

State level:

Policy interventions (for states and ULBs):

- Introduced a landfill tax for dumping or disposing of waste in landfills.
- Banned the disposal of recyclables in landfills.
- Promoted “Zero Waste to Landfill” through Concessionaires and Residents Welfare Associations (RWAs).

Infrastructure interventions:

- Created ULB-level dashboards to track dry waste collection and management.
- Facilitated tie-ups with manufacturers under EPR.

Action Plan for Waste Circularity (*MoHUA, 2021*)

National level:

Policy interventions:

- GST for C&D waste products has been reduced from 18% to 5%.
- The green tax for the transportation of C&D waste products is waived for C&D waste products.
- The electricity load in the C&D waste plant charged at the industrial rate is reduced suitably.

- Tax concessions and/or incentives to set up STPs, like in the form of tax reductions on equipment by the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Jalshakti.

State level:

Policy interventions (for states and ULBs):

- Setting up a state-level Wastewater Recycling & Reuse Fund by the state governments
- Incentives (like municipal tax benefits) for residential societies with environmental clearance and having in-situ STPs with reuse capacity upto 40% of treated wastewater to be monitored and encouraged by both state governments and ULBs.

Recommendations:

- Building products and materials with secondary resources to be given tax rebates
- Waste generators must pay charges for collection, transportation, processing, and disposal as notified by the concerned authorities.
- Concession agreements with processing plants should be for a minimum of 15 years

Recommendations and Action Plans for Treated Sludge (*MoHUA, 2021*)

National level:

Policy interventions:

- Customs/GST exemption on equipment under the Ministry of Finance on the use of plants/machinery to make biogas, to electricity plants, and sludge dewatering equipment
- Incentivizing by-products and tag sale with chemical fertilizers under the Ministry of Chemicals & Fertilizers
- Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas to incentivise through a mechanism of buying biogas produced from sludge

State level:

Policy interventions (for states and ULBs):

- A heavy tax/fine on dumping sludge in landfills/open land by state pollution control boards (SPCB) and the ULBs (also monitoring these dumping grounds).

Current Financial Incentive Models and Their Applications

Several distinct financial models to address the challenges of waste management are as follows:

- **Blended Finance:** This model combines public, private, and philanthropic funds to de-risk investments in waste infrastructure.

- **Purpose:** To mobilize private capital for large-scale waste-to-energy plants and enhance recycling rates and resource recovery.
- **Application:** Pune is a major example that follows this strategy through collaborations with social enterprises and corporate partnerships, and is supported by Swachh Bharat Mission-Urban (SBM-U) funding. Bengaluru also uses blended finance for tech-driven waste-to-energy projects (*Bhowmick & Bhalla, 2025*).
- **Green Municipal Bonds:** These are financial instruments specifically earmarked for environmental projects, funding sustainable infrastructure. Here, the debt securities are issued by local governments to mobilize capital exclusively for sustainable waste management, recycling, and clean energy initiatives.
 - **Purpose:** Channeling capital into vital waste management facilities like recycling plants and waste-to-energy facilities, aligning with SDG 11 on Sustainable Cities.
 - **Application:** This was piloted in Pune and Ghaziabad, India. Projects in Mumbai for Material Recovery Facilities (MRFs) and awareness campaigns could also benefit (*Bhowmick & Bhalla, 2025*).
- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Credits:** Mandates that hold producers accountable for post-consumer waste, thereby creating markets for recycling credits.
 - **Purpose:** To streamline EPR compliance, formalize waste collection, reduce leakage, and improve transparency within the waste value chain.
 - **Application:** Hyderabad-based Recykal, a digital Producer Responsibility Organisation (PRO), facilitates EPR compliance by connecting brands with recyclers via a cloud-based platform.
- **Pay-As-You-Throw (PAYT) Schemes:** These schemes charge residents based on the volume or weight of non-recyclable waste they generate.
 - **Purpose:** To incentivize source segregation of waste and reduce reliance on landfills, aligning with SDG 12 on Responsible Consumption.
 - **Application:** A pilot in Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala, reduced landfill dependency by up to 30 percent. The SBM-U also focuses on segregation at source in cities like Indore (*Bhowmick & Bhalla, 2025*).
- **Deposit Refund Systems (DRS):** This model requires consumers to pay a refundable deposit on certain plastic items.

- **Purpose:** To substantially reduce littering and empower local communities to become environmental stewards.
- **Application:** Meghalaya's Green Deposit Scheme requires tourists to pay an INR 100 refundable deposit for plastic items carried into eco-sensitive zones like Nongriat's living root bridges, managed by village councils (*Bhowmick & Bhalla, 2025*).
- **Results-Based Financing (RBF) / Payments:** This approach links funding disbursements to the achievement of pre-agreed, measurable outcomes.
 - **Purpose:** To incentivize specific improvements in waste management services and financial sustainability.
 - **Application:** In Nepal, RBF helped in the expansion of waste collection to 120,000 households (*Zhang et al., 2025*). China's Ningbo project also managed to improve waste segregation and recycling for over 900,000 households through this process. Liberia's project linked payments to targets for female street sweepers and waste pickers and supported community cleanliness campaigns (*World Bank Group, 2025*).
- **Carbon Offset Projects and Emission Reduction Credits:** These generate revenue through the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.
 - **Purpose:** To support the operations of landfills and provide clean energy.
 - **Application:** In Monterrey, Mexico, a carbon offset project generated revenue by selling over 1 million metric tons of CO2 equivalent (mtCO2e) of certified emission reductions. It also supported landfill operations and provided clean energy to 730,000 people (*World Bank Group, 2025*).
- **Sustainability-Linked Loans and Bonds:** These financial instruments are linked to achieving specific sustainability performance targets.
 - **Purpose:** To finance waste treatment and recovery infrastructure while aligning with environmental goals.
 - **Application:** In 2023, the International Finance Corporation provided a 130 million BRL (Brazilian Reais) sustainability-linked loan to Brazil for a material recovery facility and leachate treatment. In 2024, the World Bank Treasury issued a 100 million USD Plastic Waste Reduction-Linked Bond and raised 14 million USD for plastic waste collection and recycling projects in Indonesia and Ghana (*World Bank Group, 2025*).

Effectiveness and Challenges

The implementation of these financial incentives has yielded significant results, but it also faces significant hurdles:

- **Effectiveness:**

Improved Waste Management Services: Support from the World Bank has led to increasing waste collection, improving segregation and recycling, and increasing disposal at sanitary landfills in countries like Nepal, China, and Tanzania (*World Bank Group, 2025*).

Strengthened Institutions: Projects in Bosnia and Herzegovina allowed for the establishment of intermunicipal boards, thereby reducing the unserved population from 75% to 34% (*Zhang et al., 2025*). Morocco developed a solid waste governance framework, increasing national collection coverage from 44% to 96% (*World Bank Group, 2025*).

Enhanced Financial Sustainability: Mexico's carbon offset project has managed to generate much-needed revenue for landfill operations (*World Bank Group, 2025*).

Social Inclusion: In Liberia, projects have strengthened community-based enterprises, formalized waste pickers, and trained female street sweepers, ultimately benefiting nearly 700,000 people (*World Bank Group, 2025*).

Dedicated Projects vs. Components: Dedicated MSWM projects, where nearly 100% of commitment is for SWM objectives, show significantly higher success rates (73% moderately satisfactory or better outcomes) compared to projects where SWM is a smaller component (62%). Long-term, well-sequenced, and coherent engagement also correlates with better outcomes (*World Bank Group, 2022*).

- **Challenges:**

Government Commitment and Financial Sustainability: Often, due to a lack of political commitment or competing demands for public funds, it is difficult for governments to ensure sustainable financing. Despite initial successes, cost recovery often declines post-project. This has led to reduced resources for upkeep and a relapse into unsustainable practices like open dumping (*World Bank Group, 2022*).

Policy and Regulatory Gaps: India's green bond market is nascent and faces regulatory complexities and low investor awareness. Furthermore, municipal corporations often lack the technical expertise to design bankable projects. The *World Bank Group (2022)* report states

that these inconsistent policy enforcement and fragmented waste streams end up hindering the effectiveness of blended finance.

Informal Sector Integration: EPR compliance is usually spread unevenly, especially among small businesses. And informal waste pickers, who handle a significant portion of India's plastic waste, face exploitation and unsafe practices.

Behavioral Resistance and Enforcement: PAYT schemes face several hurdles due to behavioral resistance and inadequate enforcement. In rural areas, persistent open burning and dumping are caused by weak collection systems. DRS systems in remote areas encounter logistical issues like limited refill stations and strained enforcement during peak tourist seasons (*World Bank Group, 2022*).

Political Economy and Accountability: Lack of transparency and vested interests within the waste sector can impede progress. The ability to monitor service delivery and assign accountability is often weak. Political changes and a lack of sustained commitment across administrations can derail projects.

Land Availability: The "not-in-my-backyard" (NIMBY) phenomenon, coupled with unreliable land administration and poor urban planning, makes acquiring land for landfills and other waste infrastructure a systematic constraint, leading to project delays and opposition (*World Bank Group, 2022*).

Potential for Future Growth

The future of monetizing waste for sustainable development relies on addressing the above-mentioned challenges through a combination of technological innovation, strong international cooperation, and integrated policy frameworks:

- **Technological Innovation:** Emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled waste sorting, blockchain for tracking EPR credits, and chemical recycling can significantly enhance efficiency and transparency across the waste value chain. Organizations like Blue Planet and India's Lucro Plastecycle are already leveraging these innovations (*Bhowmick & Bhalla, 2025*).
- **Enhanced Multilateral Cooperation and Financing:** The UN Environment Assembly Resolution 5/14 launched the current discussions for a legally binding international convention on plastic pollution, highlighting the world's commitment to a coordinated response that addresses the entire lifetime of plastics.

- In an attempt to incorporate climate finance methods, India has suggested creating a special global fund to assist developing nations in putting plastic reduction plans into action.
- **Integrated Planning and Green Finance:** Indian cities are encouraged to align their waste strategies with Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Integrated planning that harmonizes climate and waste targets will be essential to access green climate finance.
- **Continued World Bank Support:** The World Bank Group continues to persist in assisting LMICs by strengthening policies, institutions, infrastructure, financial sustainability, community engagement, and social inclusion of informal waste pickers and women. The World Bank Group continues expanding international cooperation and financing for SWM, emphasizing integrated, locally tailored strategies that prioritize waste reduction, recycling, and resource recovery. Global initiatives like the Global Plastics Treaty, Methane Abatement Pledge, and Paris Agreement offer opportunities to advance sustainable waste management.

Ultimately, by combining domestic innovations with international momentum, India and other developing nations have the potential to curb their plastic waste and set precedents for building sustainable, resilient urban futures.

In the case of India: A brief overview of the current status

Model	Purpose	Application in India (and source)	Effectiveness
Blended Finance	Combine public, private, and philanthropic funds to de-risk investments	Pune’s PPP with SWaCH Cooperative <i>(Results-Based Financing for Municipal Solid Waste, 2014)</i>	“60 MT of waste is diverted away from landfills per day, with 80-85% of the waste generated in the city being recycled/processed, resulting in annual GHG emission savings of approximately 50,000 tonnes of CO2.” Shows strong results in inclusion & cost efficiency.

Green Municipal Bonds (Muni Bonds)	Debt instruments earmarked for sustainable waste infra	Ghaziabad (2021): Tertiary Water treatment plant. Ahmedabad (2023): Green energy generation. Vadodara (2024): Sewage treatment plant and drainage systems. These four muni bonds are worth ₹694 crore (<i>Dutta, 2025</i>).	The total value of municipal bonds outstanding in India is ₹4,204 crore (as of March 2024), which is only 0.09% of the overall corporate bond market. And there has been a rise in muni green bond issuances since 2021 (<i>Bibhudatta & Rathee, 2025</i>).
Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Credits	Make producers accountable for post-consumer waste via tradable credits	Recykal (Hyderabad) digital PRO connects brands to recyclers (<i>Bhadra & Paramita Mishra, 2021</i>).	The amount of waste collected daily increased from 20 to 30 kg initially to about 10,000 to 15,000 kg per day (as of 2021).
Pay-As-You-Throw (PAYT)	Charge households based on waste volume/weight to incentivize segregation	Thiruvananthapuram (pilot), Indore (SBM-U supported segregation at source) - (<i>Pasricha, 2024</i>) (<i>Waste Mgmt, n.d.</i>)	In T'puram, there are 25.12 lakh source waste processing units across the state. Households using these facilities are given a 5% discount on their property tax as an incentive. In Indore, vehicles collect waste from households and business establishments and segregate it into six categories. It has won the cleanest city award for 8 years in a row.
Deposit Refund	Refundable deposit for	Meghalaya's "Green Deposit" (₹100 refundable) for tourists in	Early reports suggest improved compliance & reduced littering around living root bridges.

System (DRS)	plastic items to reduce litter	eco-sensitive zones - (Govt. of Meghalaya - Office Memorandum, 2024)	However, detailed data is absent. (OT staff, 2025)
Results-Based Financing (RBF)	Link payments to verified outcomes	(Review of Results-Based Financing Schemes in WASH, 2015) (Results-Based Financing for Municipal Solid Waste, 2014)	On average, RBF projects delivered about 94 percent of targeted outputs, i.e., RBF projects tend to convert inputs into the desired outputs (2015 Report).
Carbon Offset / Emission Credits	Generate revenue via GHG reductions in waste projects	Mostly international, but India is now focusing on it (From Delhi to Paris: India on the Path to Resilient Urban Waste Management, 2025)	India's government has approved a list of ten sectors to participate in its voluntary carbon market under the Carbon Credit Trading Scheme – other results are scarce.

Table 1: Effectiveness table

Discussion

This report shows that financial incentives — like tax rebates, subsidies, EPR, PAYT schemes, and blended finance — play an important role in promoting sustainable waste management. In India, measures like GST reductions for recycled products, subsidies for biogas and compost, and direct financial assistance highlight the concrete efforts to support circularity. Globally, tools like green bonds, sustainability-linked loans, and results-based financing reflect growing innovation in waste sector financing.

The evidence provided in this report suggests these incentives improve waste collection, recycling, and financial sustainability, while also supporting social inclusion by formalizing waste pickers and engaging women in the waste economy. However, the success of these

endeavors depends heavily on infrastructure, governance, and enforcement. Dedicated, long-term projects consistently perform better than fragmented or short-term initiatives.

The review has some limitations, which are discussed in detail in the subsequent section. Many sources describe policy intentions rather than long-term impacts, and newer schemes (for example, India's Green Credit Programme) lack outcome data. Methodologically, restricting the review to post-2020 sources and excluding opinion-based materials narrowed the evidence base but also reduced the historical context and personal or grassroots level impact of these schemes.

Overall, in short, these findings point to the need for stronger policy frameworks, integration of informal systems, and sustained financing. For practice and policy, this means embedding incentives within wider governance and infrastructure reforms. And for future research, there is a clear need to evaluate long-term effectiveness and capture community-level perspectives.

Conclusion and Future Directions

Conclusion

To conclude, the main implication of this research is that financial incentives are powerful tools for promoting sustainable waste management, but these are not and cannot be standalone solutions. Incentives are most effective when embedded within broader institutional, regulatory, and social frameworks that ensure enforcement, inclusion, and transparency. By linking financial incentives to measurable sustainability outcomes, governments and stakeholders can reduce landfill dependence, improve recycling, and create inclusive urban economies. However, gaps in implementation and uneven success across contexts highlight the urgent need for policies that are adaptive, equitable, and grounded in long-term sustainability planning.

Future Direction

This review has faced several constraints that have restricted the scope and depth of this research. Methodologically, the exclusion of pre-2020 data limited historical analysis, and the reliance on qualitative sources limited the ability to assess quantitative effectiveness. The search process was restricted to certain repositories and may not have captured all relevant evidence. Furthermore, the review did not include primary data collection from communities

or businesses, which could have provided a richer and more realistic picture of how incentives operate in practice.

Future research could address these gaps by:

- Conducting longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term effectiveness of financial incentives such as EPR credits, PAYT, and subsidies.
- Collecting primary data from waste workers, MSMEs, and local communities to assess real-world impacts of incentives and barriers to participation.
- Expanding comparative analysis across different countries and/or regions to understand which models are most transferable and effective.
- Incorporating technological innovations such as AI-enabled waste tracking into future evaluations of financial incentive mechanisms.
- Exploring how financial incentives can be better integrated with climate finance and international agreements to align waste management with broader sustainability goals.

By pursuing these directions, future work can build stronger evidence on how to design, implement, and sustain financial incentives that are effective, inclusive, and adaptable to rapidly changing urban contexts.

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